

Biosorption of heavy metals by *Rhizopus arrhizus* and *Aspergillus niger*

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Biosorption of four heavy metals Pb, Cd, Ni and Cr by *Rhizopus arrhizus* and *Aspergillus niger* during their active growth was observed to develop strains to remove heavy metals from industrial waste waters. Among four metals tested for biosorption from synthetic growth media containing 1 mg/l of the metals, *R. arrhizus* showed maximum biosorption (45.54%) in case of Pb whereas *A. niger* showed maximum biosorption (59.67%) in case of Cd. A strain of *R. arrhizus* adapted to 100 mg/l Pb absorbed 57.77% of Pb and that of *A. niger* adapted to 100 mg/l Cd absorbed 91.59% of Cd during active growth. EDTA extraction studies showed that 78–85% of Pb was associated with cell surface of *R. arrhizus* and 60–65% of Cd associated with the cell surface of *A. niger*.

Several physical and chemical processes have been developed for removal of heavy metals from water, which include chemical precipitation, chemical oxidation or reduction, filtration or ion-exchange. But these processes are inapposite when small concentrations of heavy metals are present in the waste waters (1 to 100 mg/l)¹. Processes involving ion-exchange resins for metal removal are also very expensive. So, the current interest in the use of microorganisms in live or dead condition² for the removal of nitrogen, phosphorus and metals from commercial and municipal waste waters³ is growing fast. It has been established that *Rhizopus arrhizus*⁴ and *Aspergillus niger*⁵ possess great metal absorption capacities in inactivated form. Recently, Price *et al.*⁶ have established that *A. niger* absorbs high amounts of zinc and copper from aqueous solutions during active growth. This suggests that these two microorganisms can be used for bioremediation of heavy metals from aqueous solutions.

In the present study, the ability of *R. arrhizus* and *A. niger* to remove heavy metals from aqueous solutions has been studied in laboratory conditions. It has also been studied that the capacity of metal absorption can be increased if the microorganisms are previously adapted in higher concentrations of the metals. The aim of the present study was also to develop strains of *R. arrhizus* and *A. niger* that can be applied to remove heavy metals from industrial waste waters during active growth. Industrial waste waters contain varying concentrations of heavy metals, which may be lethal to the microorganisms when the concentrations were much higher. Therefore, chances of survival will be increased if the strains were adapted to high concentrations of the metals.

Results and Discussion

Four toxic heavy metals, viz. lead, cadmium, nickel and chromium were studied for their effects upon the growth of *R. arrhizus* and *A. niger*. During the growth of the microorganisms in the culture medium containing different concentrations of heavy metals, the microorganisms absorbed metals and the biosorption capacities were different for different metals. Table 1 shows, the results of extent of biosorption of the four metals by the two microorganisms. *R. arrhizus* and *A. niger* show maximum biosorption of 45.54% in case of Pb and 59.67% in case of Cd when the concentration of the metals was 1 mg/l in the synthetic growth medium. The heavy metals were toxic to both the microorganisms, which is evident from the decreased cellular growth with increasing metal concentration in comparison to the control containing no metal. This means that the growth of the organisms plays a role in the absorption of the metals. However, in very low metal concentration (i.e. 0.5 mg/l), the biosorption is low despite higher cellular growth. This may be due to the fact that when metal cation binding sites on the cell wall are mostly occupied, then metal ions begin to move inside the cell. In low concentration of metals, the cell wall binding sites may not be occupied completely so that only a small amount of the metal could move inside which is evident from Table 1. This was also observed by Murray and Kidby⁷ with yeast cells, grown in mercury solutions where increasing mercury concentrations in the medium led to higher levels of the metals inside the cytoplasm.

In case of *R. arrhizus*, the pH is minimum when maximum absorption of the four metals occurred. This means that proton might be released during binding of the metals to the cell wall and the release of proton is higher with higher

Table 1. Percent biosorption of heavy metals by *R. arrhizus* and *A. niger* from synthetic growth media containing different concentrations of metal

Initial pH of the medium = 4.5 at 0 day of incubation.

Concn. of Pb mg/l	<i>R. arrhizus</i>					<i>A. niger</i>				
	Bio-sorption %	Metal bound to cell surface %	Metal inside the cell %	Cell dry wt. g/l	Final pH of the medium after 7 days of incubation	Bio-sorption %	Metal bound to cell surface %	Metal inside the cell %	Cell dry wt. g/l	Final pH of the medium after 7 days of incubation
0	00.00	00.00	00.00	4.24	3.0	00.00	00.00	00.00	18.57	4.1
0.5	43.48	35.04	8.44	3.93	2.5	44.33	28.48	15.85	17.33	4.1
1.0	45.54	35.52	10.02	3.56	2.3	47.03	28.88	18.15	16.84	4.4
1.5	44.07	33.49	10.58	3.65	2.3	42.32	27.08	15.24	14.15	4.3
2.0	41.77	31.33	10.44	3.38	2.6	40.54	25.54	15.00	13.69	4.2
3.0	35.28	25.05	10.23	2.97	3.0	36.83	23.20	13.63	11.52	4.2
4.0	28.05	19.64	8.41	2.42	3.1	25.35	15.72	9.63	9.09	4.0
5.0	21.79	15.25	6.54	2.02	3.3	19.80	12.28	7.52	8.47	4.0
Concn. of Cd mg/l										
0	00.00	00.00	00.00	4.16	2.9	00.00	00.00	00.00	18.42	4.2
0.5	40.09	31.27	8.80	3.72	2.2	52.65	33.70	18.95	17.26	4.3
1.0	41.52	31.56	9.96	3.83	2.3	59.67	35.59	24.08	17.58	4.5
1.5	42.36	31.77	10.59	3.80	2.1	52.75	33.23	19.52	16.24	4.5
2.0	41.37	30.15	11.72	3.61	2.4	49.67	31.29	18.38	12.68	4.3
3.0	40.08	28.46	11.62	3.51	2.9	40.15	25.29	14.86	9.86	4.2
4.0	37.72	26.40	11.32	3.29	3.2	36.83	22.83	14.00	7.43	4.0
5.0	36.85	25.06	11.79	3.03	3.3	30.05	18.63	11.42	5.71	4.0
Concn. of Ni mg/l										
0	00.00	00.00	00.00	4.25	3.0	00.00	00.00	00.00	18.61	4.2
0.5	26.55	21.77	4.78	3.42	2.9	40.67	26.44	14.23	18.13	4.3
1.0	28.00	22.40	5.60	3.43	2.8	46.84	29.98	16.86	18.15	4.3
1.5	28.13	21.94	6.19	3.40	2.6	48.11	30.31	17.80	18.32	4.4
2.0	29.37	23.20	6.17	3.39	2.4	52.70	32.67	20.03	18.50	4.6
3.0	27.42	21.11	6.31	3.12	2.8	45.37	28.13	17.24	17.22	4.4
4.0	22.81	16.08	6.73	2.96	3.2	41.18	24.91	15.27	16.62	4.3
5.0	18.67	11.75	6.92	2.65	3.6	36.31	22.51	13.80	15.81	4.1
Concn. of Cr mg/l										
0	00.00	00.00	00.00	4.19	3.0	00.00	00.00	00.00	18.53	4.2
0.5	40.32	32.66	7.66	3.43	2.3	49.23	32.00	17.23	18.11	4.3
1.0	42.56	34.05	8.51	3.24	2.2	50.15	32.10	18.05	18.34	4.3
1.5	42.04	33.41	8.63	3.16	2.4	56.90	36.41	20.49	18.48	4.5
2.0	41.79	32.84	8.95	3.04	2.4	52.55	33.11	19.44	18.06	4.4
3.0	39.25	30.08	9.17	2.85	2.6	48.06	30.28	17.78	17.43	4.4
4.0	36.87	27.19	9.68	2.57	2.8	46.51	29.30	17.21	17.09	4.1
5.0	33.77	23.93	9.84	2.39	3.2	38.25	23.72	14.53	16.68	4.0

percentage of biosorption, indicated by the decrease of pH after 7 days of incubation with respect to the initial pH of the medium (i.e. pH = 4.5 at 0 day of incubation). Gupta *et al.*⁸ also stated that ion-exchange process is involved in metal biosorption where protons or metal cations may be liberated against uptake of heavy metals. However, in case of *A. niger*, the change in pH was not appreciable with respect to the initial pH of the medium (pH 4.5). In this case, appreciable amounts of the metal might have moved inside the intracellular components of the biomass and are not associated with cell surface where mainly ion-exchange takes place. The results (Table 1) show that appreciable amount of metals enter inside the cell in case of *A. niger* in comparison to *R. arrhizus* when the metal concentration in the synthetic culture medium is similar.

In case of both the microorganisms, decrease in the cellular dry weight with increasing metal concentrations indicates that high concentrations of the metals are toxic towards the microorganisms. Toxicity could be reduced and the microorganisms could absorb more metal if the organisms were adapted to higher concentrations of the metals, which was successfully carried out in case of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} accumulation by *Candida* sp. reported by Donmez and Aksu⁹.

To achieve high concentration of lead resistant strain of *R. arrhizus* and high concentration of cadmium resistant strain of *A. niger*, the spores from the parent strains were incubated in the synthetic growth media containing high concentrations of the respective metals. High concentrations of metal resistant variants having better biosorption capacities than the parent strain were called productive variants. 100 strains were isolated from each of seven different concentrations of lead in the synthetic growth media in case of *R. arrhizus* and 100 strains were isolated also from each of seven different concentrations of cadmium in the synthetic growth media in case of *A. niger*. Productive variants were selected from the adapted strains (data not shown) and their metal absorption capacities were tested with respect to the parent strain.

Metal absorption capacities of the productive variants in case of both the microorganisms were compared to the parent strains using the same culture conditions and same metal concentrations. Table 2 shows the lead and cadmium biosorption capacities of the productive variants of *R. arrhizus* and *A. niger*, respectively, adapted in different concentrations of corresponding metals. The data reveal that if the parent strain is adapted to a higher concentration of metal, minimum biosorption of the metal shown by a productive variant is always more than the productive variant adapted

to a lower concentration of the metal. It is also revealed that microorganisms adapted to higher concentrations of the metals could effectively absorb larger amounts of metals due to their increased resistance towards the metals, which can be successfully applied for the removal of lead and cadmium from the metal bearing waste waters.

Table 2. Biosorption capacity of the high concentration of metal resistant productive variants of *R. arrhizus* and *A. niger* from synthetic growth medium containing 1 mg/l of Pb and Cd respectively

Microorganisms resistant to metal concn. mg/l	Minimum biosorption of lead shown by a productive variant of <i>R. arrhizus</i> %	Minimum biosorption of cadmium shown by a productive variant of <i>A. niger</i> %
0	45.54	59.67
10	46.83	63.74
20	49.70	66.12
30	50.68	70.68
40	52.59	76.06
50	54.48	79.59
80	55.45	85.36
100	57.77	91.59

To study the surface absorption of lead and cadmium by *R. arrhizus* and *A. niger*, respectively, the amount of metal absorbed in the cell surfaces was determined by EDTA extraction method¹⁸. It has been observed that 78.3% of lead was absorbed in the cell surface of the parent strain of *R. arrhizus* and which increased to 85.8% in case of a productive variant of *R. arrhizus* adapted to 100 mg/l of Pb (data not shown). Similarly, 60.3% of cadmium was absorbed in the cell surface of the parent strain of *A. niger* which increased to 65.9% in case of a productive variant of *A. niger* adapted to 100 mg/l of Cd (data not shown). It is evident that all surface absorption of the metals can be increased with adaptation to higher concentrations of the metals, which may be a good recovery process for lead and cadmium from dilute metal solutions.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade (Qualigens). Media preparation and volume make-up were done by double-distilled water.

Parent strains of *R. arrhizus* and *A. niger* were obtained from Bioengineering Division, Department of Chemical Engineering, University of Calcutta. The microorganisms were sub-cultured to maintain in potato dextrose agar slants¹⁰ in case of *R. arrhizus* and Czapek dox agar slants¹¹ in case of *A. niger*, both stored at 4°.

Spore suspensions were prepared as described elsewhere¹². Count of the spores in suspension was determined by conventional pour-plate technique. The concentration of the spores was adjusted to 4.5×10^7 spores/ml in case of *R. arrhizus* and 2×10^5 spores/ml in case of *A. niger* in all experiments.

The composition of the synthetic culture medium for metal uptake experiments and for the development of high concentration of metal adapted strains in case of *R. arrhizus* was (as g/100 ml): D-glucose, 2; urea, 0.6; KH_2PO_4 , 0.2; $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 0.05. Initial pH of the medium was adjusted to 4.5. In case of *A. niger*, the same was (as g/100 ml): D-glucose, 5; NaNO_3 , 0.2; KH_2PO_4 , 0.1; KCl, 0.05; $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 0.05; $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 0.01. Initial pH of the culture medium was adjusted to 4.5. A Systronics 335 pH meter was used. Stock solutions $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, $\text{Cd}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, NiSO_4 and $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ (1000 ml/l) (1000 mg/l with respect to the metals) were prepared separately. Calculated volumes of these solutions were added to the synthetic growth medium to achieve the desired metal concentrations of 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 3.0, 4.0 and 5.0 mg/l for the metal uptake studies and also for the development of high concentration of metal adapted strains. 50 ml of synthetic culture medium with the desired metal concentration as well as spore suspension was taken in 250 ml Erlenmeyer flask for the studies. All the experiments were done in quadruplicate sets and average of four values were taken.

Metal biosorption assay : Erlenmeyer Flasks with the seeded culture medium were incubated at 28° for 7 days^{13,14}. The pH of the culture medium was measured, the cell biomass was separated by filtration, washed with double-distilled water and digested with 6 N HNO_3 as described in EPA methods¹⁵. The digests were analyzed in atomic absorption spectrometer (Varian SP-20 BQ) for the metal concentrations after proper dilution¹⁶.

The metals bound to the cell surface were determined by EDTA extraction method using 10 mM EDTA¹⁷. Then the cell biomass was washed with double-distilled water and digested with 6 N HNO_3 to determine the amount of metal inside the cell.

Cellular growth was determined by drying the cell biomass at 105° to a constant weight¹⁸.

The spores in the media, after the desired incubation period at different high concentrations of the metals, were

serially diluted by pour plate technique and 100 colonies were isolated from each concentration and each colony was examined for productive variants. The isolated productive variants of *R. arrhizus* and *A. niger* were kept at 4° in respective nutrient agar slants for biosorption studies.

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